

Study of Relationship Between Spiritual Intelligence and Personality of Higher Education Students

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Received : 11/05/2025

1st BPR : 17/05/2025

2nd BPR : 25/05/2025

Accepted : 03/06/2025

Abstract

This study explores the relationship between spiritual intelligence and personality traits among higher education students. Spiritual intelligence, which is often combined with self-awareness, ethical decision-making, and emotional resilience, plays an important role in both academic and personal development. Spiritual intelligence is the primary focus of current research focusing on personality traits. Students studying in degree college of district Saharanpur of Uttar Pradesh state have been included in which 100 students, 50 boys and 50 girls have been selected as sample by simple or variable sampling method. The hypotheses were tested at 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance. The success of the research depends upon the selection of the suitable tools. The following tools were used to collect the data. Roqan Spiritual Intelligence Test by Prof. Roquiya Zainuddin and Ms. Anjum Ahmed (2012). Eysenck personality test Dr. B. Dey, and Dr.R. Thakur. After collecting the data, the obtained data of spiritual intelligence and personality traits were analyzed through Pearson correlation coefficient. The hypotheses were tested at 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance. Conclusion, a positive and highly significant relationship was found between psychological disorders and spiritual intelligence among higher level students. On the other hand, in the third hypothesis, no relationship was found between Extroversion and Spiritual intelligence and between Neurotism and Spiritual intelligence due to negative self and finally, a positive highly significant relationship was found between Lie scale and spiritual intelligence.

Keywords: Spiritual Intelligence, Personality and Higher Education Student.

Introduction

Recently, the concept of spiritual intelligence in some ancient beings has attracted attention in theories and startup research. Spiritual intelligence goes beyond religious beliefs and focuses on a person's ability to apply spiritual values in their daily lives to promote self-awareness, purpose, and interpersonal harmony. Spiritual intelligence, which is often combined with self-awareness, ethical decision-making, and emotional resilience, plays an important role in both academic and personal development. Under this, the personality traits of students affect their adaptability, academic performance and social functioning. The aim of the study of this research paper is to investigate the relationship between the traits of spiritual intelligence and personality dimensions among higher education students. A person needs self-confidence to achieve his spiritual life as well as to develop his personality, which contributes significantly in completing this task more efficiently and also motivates a person to think positively. That person tries to put himself in any situation. Only a self-confident person believes in his spirituality and personality ability and can run his life smoothly and easily.

Spiritual Intelligence (SI)

Spiritual intelligence, as defined by Zohar and Marshall (2000), is the ability to find meaning, purpose, and ethical values in life. SI includes components such as self-awareness, transcendence,

compassion, and wisdom. Studies suggest that higher SI correlates with greater emotional stability and resilience.

The Big Four Personality Traits

The Four-Factor Model (FFM) classifies personality into four key dimensions:

1. Psychotism – Creativity and curiosity.
2. Extraversion – Sociability and assertiveness.
3. Neuroticism – Emotional instability and anxiety.
4. Lie scale – Discipline and responsibility.

Prior research suggests that personality traits influence emotional intelligence and coping mechanisms, making it essential to examine their connection with spiritual intelligence.

Spiritual Intelligence

Spiritual intelligence is a full picture of human intelligence which increases the human ability to connect to a higher power and a sacred entity. Those who have a higher level of spiritual intelligence are more flexible and self-conscious and have a holistic attitude to the existence and hardships of life.

Definitions of Spiritual Intelligence

In the present study, Spiritual intelligence is the ability to access, express and process spiritual information. It includes spiritual understanding, beliefs, efforts, outlook and reasoning.

Personality

Personality, a characteristic way of thinking, feeling, and behaving. Personality embraces moods, attitudes, and opinions and is most clearly expressed in interactions with other people. It includes behavioral characteristics, both inherent and acquired, that distinguish one person from another and that can be observed in people's relations to the environment and to the social group.

Definition of Personality

Personality refers to the enduring characteristics and behavior that comprise a person's unique adjustment to life, including major traits, interests, drives, values, self-concept, abilities, and emotional patterns. Various theories explain the structure and development of personality in different ways, but all agree that personality helps determine behavior.

Significance of the study

The study of spiritual intelligence relies on self-reporting. A selfassessment which positively checked the validity of the criterion and defined validity. This study will tell us about the measurement of spiritual intelligence among higher education students. The higher aspect of intelligence is spiritual intelligence. Spiritual intelligence operates the attributes and capacities of the genuine self in the form of empathy, insight, cohesion, delight, imagination, affection and peace. This study will show the result in a perception of profound motive and sense, merged with refinements in a broad range of major skills of work and skills of life. To be 'spiritual' is to think, act and interact from an awareness of self as spirit not form, soul not body. In order to understand spiritual intelligence, it is essential to distinguish it from spirituality for further conceptual clarity. Having Intelligence is to use what you know in the right way at the right time in the right place with the right intention.

Problem of the statement

"Study Of Relationship Between Spiritual Intelligence and Personality of Higher Education Students."

Objectives of Research

To study the relationship between Spiritual intelligence and Psychotism of Higher Education Student.
To study the relationship between Spiritual intelligence and Extroversion of Higher Education Student.
To study the relationship between Spiritual intelligence and Neuroticism of Higher Education Student.
To study the relationship between Spiritual intelligence and Lie scale of Higher Education Student.

Hypotheses of Research

There is no significant relationship between Spiritual intelligence and Psychotism of Higher Education Student.

There is no significant relationship between Spiritual intelligence and Extroversion of Higher Education Student.

There is no significant relationship between Spiritual intelligence and Neuroticism of Higher Education Student.

There is no significant relationship between Spiritual intelligence and Lie scale of Higher Education Student.

Delimitations of the Research

The data is delimited to:

1. Saharanpur district of Uttar Pradesh only.
2. 100 higher education students.
3. U.P. Government Aided Colleges.
4. Higher education students.
5. The variables of spiritual intelligence and personality.

Methodologies and Research design

Variables

Independent Variable

Independent variable is that variable which represents the reason for an outcome. Whenever there is a change in the dependent variable it is generally occurred by a change in the independent variable. In the present study spiritual intelligence is the independent variable.

Dependent Variable

Dependent variable is that which is dependent upon independent variable. The dependent variable is affected by the change in independent variable. The dependent variable in the present study is personality.

Research design

Descriptive research design is used for the present study. This research design is most important and widely used research design in education. This descriptive design demands certain sample and tools of research for the successful operation of the study. Below is given the detail regarding the research tools and sample which are used in this study:

Research tools

For successful completion of the research, the selection of the tools is very important. The success of the research depends upon the selection of the suitable tools. The following tools were used to collect the data:-

Roqan Spiritual Intelligence Test by Prof. Roquiya Zainuddin and Ms. AnjumAhmed (2012).

Eysenck personality test Dr. B. Dey, and Dr.R. Thakur.

Population

All higher education student of Saharanpur district. Will constitute the population of the study.

J.V.JAIN Degree College, Saharanpur

Rajkiya Degree College Nanauta, Saharanpur

Sampling technique

The present study is of descriptive nature. The sample of the present study consists of 100 higher education students. The researcher used the randomization technique of sampling to collect the data from two colleges of Saharanpur district of U.P. The selection of colleges was done after obtaining the list of all colleges of Saharanpur district and then applying the lottery system. One section from each class of B.Sc. and Independent Variable Dependent Variable Spiritual Intelligence personality 9 B.A. was selected via lottery system. 50 students out of total 100 students of B.A. and 60 students out of total 100 students of B.Sc. were selected via systematic random sampling technique.

Statistical techniques

The formulated hypotheses will be tested by employing inferential statistics. Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation will be applied to study the relationship between variables. The other techniques that will be used to study the variables are mentioned below:

- Measure of central tendency mean.
- Standard deviation.
- Karl Pearson's coefficient of Correlation(r).
- Graphical representation of the data.

Analysis and Interpretation of the study

Hypothesis(1) There is no consequence relationship between Spiritual intelligence and Psychotism of Higher Education Student.

A pearson coefficient of correlation has been computed between two variables.

Coefficient of correlation between Spiritual intelligence and Psychotism of Higher Education Student.

Table No.1 show that the spiritual intelligence of higher education students correlated with extroversion component of personality as the value coefficient of correlation 'r' comes to **0.208**

Table No 1

Cofficient of correlation between spiritual intelligence and Psychotism of higher education students.

Dimensions	Size of sample(N)	r - value
Pyschotism component of Personality and Spiritual Intelligence	100	0.208

The null hypothesis has been rejected and it has been conclude that the relationship between the spiritual intelligence and psychotism of higher education student is significantly correlated in positive direction, which means the spiritual intelligence of higher education students affect their psychotism.

Hypothesis(2) There is no consequence relationship between Spiritual intelligence and Extroverion of Higher Education Student.

A pearson coefficient of correlation has been computed between two variables.

Coefficient of correlation between Spiritual intelligence and Extroversion of Higher Education Student.

Table no.2 show that the spiritual intelligence of higher education students correlated with extroversion component of personality as the value coefficient of correlation 'r' comes to **-0.168**

Table No. 2

Cofficient of correlation between spiritual intelligence and Extroversion of higher education students.

Dimensions	Size of sample(N)	r - value
Extroversion component of Personality and Spiritual Intelligence	100	-0.168

The null hypothesis has been accepted and it has been conclude that the relationship between the spiritual intelligence and psychotism of higher education student is significantly correlated in positive direction, which means the spiritual intelligence of higher education studentsnot affect their Extroversion.

Hypothesis(3) There is no consequence relationship between Spiritual intelligence and Neuroticism of Higher Education Student.

A pearson coefficient of correlation has been computed between two variables.

Coefficient of correlation between Spiritual intelligence and Neuroticism of Higher Education Student.

Table No.3 show that the spiritual intelligence of higher education students correlated with neuroticism component of personality as the value coefficient of correlation 'r' comes to **-210**

Table No.2

Coefficient of correlation between spiritual intelligence and Neuroticism of higher education students.

Dimensions	Size of sample(N)	r - value
Neuroticism component of Personality and Spiritual Intelligence	100	-210

The null hypothesis has been accepted and it has been conclude that the relationship between the spiritual intelligence and neuroticism of higher education student is significantly correlated in positive direction, which means the spiritual intelligence of higher education students not affect their Neuroticism.

Hypothesis(4) There is no consequence relationship between Spiritual intelligence and Lie scale of Higher Education Student.

A pearson coefficient of correlation has been computed between two variables.

Coefficient of correlation between Spiritual intelligence and Lie scale of Higher Education Student.

Table No.3 show that the spiritual intelligence of higher education students correlated with Lie scale component of personality as the value coefficient of correlation 'r' comes to **+190**

Table No.2

Coefficient of correlation between spiritual intelligence and Lie scale of higher education students.

Dimensions	Size of sample(N)	r - value
Lie scale component of Personality and Spiritual Intelligence	100	0.190

The null hypothesis has been rejected and it has been conclude that the relationship between the spiritual intelligence and Lie scale of higher education student is significantly correlated in positive direction, which means the spiritual intelligence of higher education students affect their Lie scale.

Conclusion and Discussion:

Conclusion (1): The significant relationship between spiritual intelligence and psychotism of higher education students is positive correlated, which indicate the spiritual intelligence is affect the psychotism of higher education of students.

Conclusion (2): The significant relationship between spiritual intelligence and extroversion of higher education students is correlated in negative direction, which means students. Students wants to study in higher classes in which which means the spiritual intelligence of higher education students not affect their Extroversion.

Conclusion (3): The significant relationship between spiritual intelligence and Neuroticism of higher education students is correlated in negative direction, which means the spiritual intelligence of higher education students not affect their neuroticism

Conclusion (4): The significant relationship between spiritual intelligence and Lie scale of higher education students is positive correlated, which indicate the spiritual intelligence is affect the Lie scale of higher education of students.

Final conclusion

The study found a significant correlation between spiritual intelligence and personality traits of higher education students

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